

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OLIVIER****FIRST NAME: AGBON****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Comparison between British and American English.

- Two different types of English.
- They are more similar than different.¹**
- American English is the best, as the USA are the world's leading power.
- British English is the best because of the colonizer.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 25.

2. Temporality of the research project.

- A research project begins with searching the internet or heading to the library.
- A research project begins well before you search the internet or head for the library and continues long after you have collected all the data you think you need.²**
- A research project begins when you have collected all the data you think you need.
- A research project begins well before you search for the library or the internet and stops after collecting all the data you think you need.

3. Characteristic of the primary source.

- Primary sources provide you with the “raw” data or evidence.
- Primary sources are “original” materials that provide the “raw” data or evidence.³**
- Primary sources are materials that provide you with the “original” and “raw” data or evidence.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23.

³ *Ibid.*, 36.

- Primary sources include specialized encyclopedias and dictionaries that offer essays written by scholars in a field.

4. **Characteristics of bibliographic notes and bibliographic entries.**

- The bibliographic notes present the author's last name before the first name.
- Bibliographic entries present the author's first name before the last name.⁴**
- Bibliographic entries avoid using location details as the page numbers.
- Bibliographic notes and bibliographic entries are more similar than different.

5. **What is your choice on the following statements?**

- If you cite tertiary sources in a scholarly argument, you will mark yourself no novice or outsider, and many readers will not take you—or your argument—seriously.
- If you cite tertiary sources in a scholarly argument, readers will take your argument seriously.
- Tertiary sources are recommended to be cited in a scholarly argument.

⁴ Ibid.

Secondary sources are recommended to be cited in a scholarly argument.⁵

6. Quote the sources online.

I start with the “Title of the article,” Title of the publication or name of the site, volume, date of publication, and URL.⁶

I start with the “Title of the article,” the site’s name, volume, publication date, and URL.

I start with the publication title, “Title of the article,” name of the site, URL, volume, and publication date.

I start with the site’s name, Title of the publication, “Title of the article,” Title of the publication or name of the site, volume, date of publication, and URL.

7. In the structure recommended for writing the thesis.

Chapter 1 contains an introduction), (research design and methodology).

⁵ Ibid., 143.

⁶ Ibid., 154.

Chapter 2 contains (Background/theories/Literature review).⁷

Chapter 3 contains the background/theories/Literature review) and the results and analysis).

Chapter 4 (results, discussion, and analysis).

8. **What is your choice on the following statements?**

The thesis concept document and thesis prospectus are more similar than different.

Each of these two concepts is a brief research proposal that describes the research problems and their resolution process, and they depend on each other.

The thesis concept document should be at most 15 pages, excluding the cover page abstract, table of contents, bibliography, and appendices, and is based on the thesis concept document.

The thesis prospectus is based on the thesis concept document.⁸

9. **A term used in the Treaties to designate a country which is not a member of the European Union to avoid any ambiguity is :**

⁷ James P. Jr. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 20.

⁸ Ibid., 3.

- Third country.
- Non-EU countries.**⁹
- The third country in the order of countries' accession to the EU.
- The third country to have ratified the treaty of the European Commission.

10. Meaning of Common.

- European Union.**¹⁰
- Common fisheries policy.
- Common agricultural.
- Common non-agricultural policy.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide, A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Eighth Ed. (European Union, 2021), 102.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 71.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Sampson, James P. Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.